

THE METHODOLOGICAL IMPORTANCE OF CREATING MODERN DICTIONARIES IN TODAY'S WORLD

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the pedagogical importance of working with dictionaries in language learning today. It explores the theoretical perspectives of leading educators and linguists in the field, as well as reflections on the historical development and formation of lexicography.

Keywords: Lexicography, working with dictionaries, language learning, methodology, evolution.

Lexicography (derived from the Greek *lexikos* – "word/dictionary" and *grapho* – "to write") has only recently become widely utilized as a formal scientific term, despite the fact that the practice of compiling dictionaries dates back to ancient times. The first attempts to explain unfamiliar words emerged in Sumerian culture (25th century BC). This tradition evolved through monolingual lexicons of Sanskrit and Ancient Greek, and later through the appearance of Arabic-Persian dictionaries in the 6th–10th centuries (translated in the 11th century), which explained the vocabulary of literary languages. In Uzbekistan, lexicography developed rapidly during the 19th and, especially, the 20th centuries. By this period, practical lexicography had accumulated vast experience, which began to be described and synthesized, leading to the formation of theoretical lexicography. The first scientific typology of dictionaries was established by the Russian scholar L. V. Shcherba (1880–1944). Currently, lexicography is considered a branch of linguistics that deals with the theory and practice of compiling dictionaries.

The types of modern dictionaries are highly diverse. Typological classification is carried out on various bases depending on the dictionary's purpose, object of description, word order, language of description, and units of description. The most fundamental basis for classification is the object of description, according to which dictionaries are divided into linguistic (philological) and encyclopedic dictionaries.

Encyclopedic dictionaries describe realities, events, and phenomena, uncovering the content of concepts related to these objects and occurrences. In such dictionaries, nouns and noun phrases – specifically proper names, surnames, and geographical names – predominate.

Linguistic dictionaries focus not on the object or concept itself, but on the word as a linguistic unit. They describe its linguistic and speech characteristics: grammatical features, lexical meaning, orthoepic (pronunciation) and stylistic properties, etymological information, and more. Depending on the objectives and methods of description, linguistic dictionaries are categorized into several types. Among these, monolingual explanatory dictionaries hold a leading position, where word meanings are explained alongside examples from various speech sources.

Explanatory dictionaries are often normative; they are guided by literary usage through examples and stylistic labels. However, there are also explanatory dictionaries that encompass not only literary vocabulary but also regional, professional, and social dialects. For instance, V.I.Dahl's "Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language" reflects the full diversity of the spoken language. Specific explanatory dictionaries include dictionaries of a writer's language, neologisms, rare words, and others. There are also etymological dictionaries that examine dictionaries from the perspective of their origin. Depending on the unit of description, dictionaries may be classified as phraseological, foreign-word, or other specialized types. In addition to explanatory ones, linguistic dictionaries include orthographic (spelling) dictionaries, orthoepic (pronunciation) dictionaries, and those reflecting word-formation principles. Alongside monolingual linguistic dictionaries, bilingual and multilingual translation dictionaries are widely represented.

Furthermore, there are dictionaries that combine the features of linguistic, encyclopedic, and ethnolinguistic reference works. Terminological dictionaries belong to this group as they contain extralinguistic information in addition to specific lexical features. Finally, with the advancement of computer technology in the modern world, a new field has emerged – electronic lexicography, which deals with the creation of electronic dictionaries. Such dictionaries can be used via computer by downloading them as software or accessing them digitally.

It is worth noting that great attention is being paid to the development of our mother tongue in our country. Today, our beloved Uzbekistan is taking bold steps into a new stage of its development based on the priority idea: "From national recovery to national prosperity." Along with all other sectors, extensive work is being carried out to increase the role and prestige of the state language in society. Simultaneously, significant emphasis is placed on the development of lexicology. Today, lexicography is evolving rapidly, and the types of dictionaries currently in development include:

Translation Dictionaries: As independent Uzbekistan opens up to the world, the emergence of bilingual and multilingual dictionaries is a result of societal needs. In addition to English-Uzbek, German-Uzbek, French-Uzbek, Persian-Uzbek, Arabic-Uzbek, and Turkish-Uzbek dictionaries, multilingual versions such as English-Russian-Uzbek are being compiled. Phrasebooks in two or more languages can also be included in this category. During the independence period, a major milestone was reached with the publication of the two-volume "Russian-Uzbek Dictionary."

Encyclopedic Dictionaries: These dictionaries do not merely explain words but clarify the objects and concepts represented by them. There have been sharp increases in the number of encyclopedic publications, such as the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan," "Encyclopedia of History," "Women's Encyclopedia," "Children's Encyclopedia," and "My First Encyclopedia: The World of Plants," among others.

Explanatory Dictionaries: Among the monumental works achieved during the independence era, the newly compiled five-volume "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" stands out as a significant phenomenon. This is the first large-scale dictionary in the history of Uzbek lexicography, containing over 80,000 words and phrases. It differs from the previous two-volume edition with several distinct advantages.

Currently, works such as the "Brief Explanatory Dictionary of Philosophy," "Explanatory Dictionary of Economic Terms," and the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Epic 'Alpomish'" are titled as explanatory dictionaries; however, in our opinion, they are distinguished by their specialized, terminological, and encyclopedic nature.

Furthermore, other types of dictionaries are increasingly covering all general and specific aspects of the language. The compilation of the "Etymological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" during the independence period was also a major event.

However, many unresolved issues remain in lexicography. For instance, D. Kalonova notes that considering the daily increasing demand and need for computers, Uzbek linguistics faces the urgent task of creating computer-specific lexicography. This involves defining the wordlist, calculating the quantity and distribution of linguistic units, modeling these units, and creating automatic translation programs. Indeed, in our age of rapid technological acceleration, creating new directions in lexicography is a requirement of the times.

Solving the problems arising from language differences in the creation of Artificial Intelligence and automatic translation requires a collaborative effort between linguists and mathematicians. Living in the 21st century, the "Age of Information," adaptation is observed in every field. For example, Nokia recently released a Mobile Dictionary program for its customers – a 38-language dictionary that pronounces words using text-to-speech technology. From this perspective, the creation of several electronic dictionaries in Uzbek (e.g., "Five-Language Computer Dictionary of Physics," 2001; "English-Uzbek Dictionary of Computer Terms," 2009) is another characteristic of the independence-era lexicography that opens new horizons for the field.

The methodology of working with dictionaries is not limited to determining word meanings; it serves to systematically understand the morphological potential and syntactic functions of words. In conclusion, the process of creating dictionaries is of strategic importance as it systematizes changes in the language's vocabulary, elevates the speech culture of society, and expands the possibility of expressing new concepts arising from scientific and technological progress in the mother tongue. Establishing a perfect lexicographical database ensures language standardization while serving as a key factor in preserving national identity and the language's prestige in the global information space. Indeed, without a rich and systematic dictionary base, high results in modern language teaching methodology and scientific communication cannot be achieved.

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